

Climate risk analysis in wind resource assessment: how to filter and select climate models ?

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Agenda

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Site-specific climate risk analysis

2

Climate model selection methods

3

Validation of climate model wind speed data using ERA5

How is global warming affecting the wind resources at our wind farms?

With a **35-year lifetime**, wind farms commissioned **today** will operate in a **substantially warmer 2061**.

Global annual surface air temperature anomalies

Data source: ERA5 • Reference period: pre-industrial (1850–1900) • Credit: C3S/ECMWF

Site-specific climate risk analysis can reveal potential future changes in wind conditions

Phase 6

- Non-downscaled **near-surface wind speed** from the SSP2-4.5 scenario
- **Multi-model ensemble** of 20 models

Annual relative wind speed changes at an Italian site

Reliable climate model selection is essential for robust local risk assessment

Using 20 climate models from Copernicus as a multi-model ensemble (MME)

Understanding which models to use in the MME

Comparing models to observations allows us to assess their empirical accuracy and select the best performing ones

We know the past from:

- Reanalysis data sets such as ERA5
- Measurements

We can compare model results to the available data from the past

Examples:

Shen et al., 2022 with measurements
Hahmann et al., 2022 with ERA5 data

Additional methods for selecting models are available in literature

At least ten ensemble members for an experiment (Deng et al., 2021)

Removing models with too coarse resolution (e.g. Martinez et al., 2023)

“Hot” models that have an unrealistic high transient climate response (Carbon Brief, 2022)

Detailed assessment of climate model performance based on comparison with ERA5

Good agreement between relative trends from ERA5 and SCADA justifies using ERA5 as reference

Several metrics are used to quantify model performance in reproducing wind speed climatology in literature

Bias

Linear trend

Frequency distribution of wind speed and direction:

- (Circular) earth mover's distance
- Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Annual cycle:

- Root-mean square error

Stilling-reversal phenomena

CMIP6 wind speed trends do not reveal any significant opposite trends to ERA5

- Applying the **Mann-Kendall test** to reveals a **significant decrease** in ERA5
- **None** of the models have a **significant opposite** trend
- We do **not** to **exclude** a model

One CMIP6 models shows artificial jump between historical and future scenarios

- We observe a **jump** from the **historic period** to the **future scenario** in **KACE-1-0-G**
- Similar jump observed at other locations
- We decide to **exclude the model** due to this inconsistency and decide to add this check to the process

The root mean square error highlights which models best reproduce the historical annual trend

The Earth Mover's Distance reveals differences in frequency distributions between climate models and ERA5

- The Wasserstein distance, also called **Earth Mover's Distance** (EMD), quantifies **work needed to transform** one distribution into another

Combining RMSE and EMD identifies a subset of best-performing climate models

- We need to define a **threshold** for filtering models
- Here, a threshold of **RMSE > 0.1, EMD > 0.9** e.g. could lead to excluding **nine models**
- Models don't necessarily fail in both metrics

Filtering models reduces the spread of projected changes between reference and operational period

- Filtering the models results in **reduced spread of projected change** between the reference and operational period
- Outliers were removed
- All models **agree** on the **sign of change** after the filtering

Conclusions

01

APPROACH TO FILTERING MODELS

There is **no clear consensus** on how to **select climate models** for wind energy applications.

There is **no established standard** on how climate models should be **filtered against ERA5** wind climatology.

02

ERA5 & SCADA

ERA5 is selected as the reference dataset because it demonstrates **good agreement** in the **relative trend** with SCADA data.

ERA5 trends at both **10 m** and **100 m** show **consistent** behavior, supporting the use of **near-surface wind speeds** from **CMIP6**.

03

IMPACT OF FILTERING MODELS

Model filtering **removes outliers** and reduces variability, leading to a more consistent multi-model ensemble.

Next steps

A

What thresholds should we set for excluding models?

B

Will we see similar impacts of filtering at other locations?

C

Can the filtering allow us to use CMIP6 results in the P50 or P90?

RWE

Thank you for your attention

